

Presentation of infinite sets of integer numbers by producing terms

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Combining and dividing infinite sets of integer numbers is a difficult problem. The lack of its satisfactory and universal solution narrows the range of possible approaches for solving problems of number theory. Here we propose a new concept for working with infinite sets of integer numbers, introducing an additional layer of *producing terms*. Then, in certain transformations one can operate on such terms instead of infinite sets, while making a connection with infinite sets when needed. For instance, consider the term $(4k+1)$ as a producer of an infinite subset of odd integers, k is an integer. We can define another producing term $(4k-1)$, producing a different infinite subset of odd integers. It is intuitively clear, if not obvious, that these two produced infinite sets of odd numbers do not intersect, while together representing the whole set of odd integers. Thus, we can represent the set of all odd integers either as two sets produced by two producing terms $(4k+1)$ and $(4k-1)$, or produced by a single term $(2k+1)$, from which these two producing terms can be derived. Now, suppose one needs to combine an infinite number of infinite subsets of pairs (or triples) of odd integers. Will this be a complete set of all possible pairs of odd integers? Will there be duplicates or, on the contrary, missing pairs? This is where the seemingly subtle distinction between the producing terms and the infinite sets they represent could be very helpful. Here, we introduce a formal apparatus to operate on infinite sets of integers using producing terms, and explore its properties.

1. Presentation of numbers in a binary form

Lemma 1: Each non-negative integer number k can be presented in a form

$$k = \sum_{i=0}^r 2^i K_i \quad (1)$$

where $K_i = \{0,1\}$.

Proof: Lemma states the known fact that any non-negative number can be presented in a binary form.

Note: Similarly, any negative integer number k can be presented as $k = \sum_{i=0}^r 2^i B_i$, where $B_i = \{-1,0\}$.

2. Presentation of pairs of odd numbers with a factor of 2^r

In the abstract, we considered single producing terms. However, such single producing terms can be united into pairs, triples, and so on, representing appropriate infinite sets of pairs, triples, etc. of integer numbers. Below, we consider pairs of odd integer numbers and their properties, and accordingly pairs of terms producing such pairs of numbers.

2.1. Introducing pairs of producing terms

Let us consider an infinite set of *pairs* of odd integers produced by a pair of terms $[(2k+1), (2p+1)]$, where k and p are *integers* $(-\infty < k, p < \infty)$, without duplicate values. The latter also means that thus produced pairs of odd integers are unique and have no duplicates too, that is there can be no the same pairs of odd integer numbers in the produced set (different order of the same integers is considered as a different pair, such as in pairs (5,9) and (9,5)). Since $(-\infty < k, p < \infty)$, this pair of terms defines *all possible* pairs of odd integers, that is the *whole set*.

The set, produced by a term $(2k+1)$, can be presented by two subterms $(4t+1)$ and $(4t+3)$, $(-\infty < t < \infty)$, with a factor of four (for the even and odd k ($k=2t, k=2t+1$)). Numbers 1 and 3 are *free coefficients* (abbreviated as FC and FCs in this paper). Each such subterm represents a subset of odd integers. Similarly, the set of odd integers $\{(2p+1)\}$, produced by the term $(2p+1)$, can be presented by two subterms $(4s+1)$ and $(4s+3)$, $(-\infty < s < \infty)$. (Here and in the entire paper such parameters as k, p, t and s , defining sets of integer numbers, are *integer* variables without duplicate values, defined on the range $(-\infty, +\infty)$). Thus, the original set of pairs of odd integers, produced by a pair of terms $[(2k+1), (2p+1)]$, can be presented by *four* possible pairs from the above subterms with a presentation factor of four (Table 1). In the following, such a pair of terms, for an arbitrary presentation level, will be called a *pair of producing terms* (PPT). PPT *defines, or produces*, a set of pairs of odd integers. Such, each of the four PPTs in row 2 and columns 1-4 of Table 1 produces an *infinite* set of pairs of odd integers. PPT $[(2k+1), (2p+1)]$ is an *initial* PPT for four derived PPTs.

Table 1. All PPTs, expressed with a factor of four, derived from initial PPT $[(2k+1), (2p+1)]$.

	0	1	2	3	4
1	k	$2t_2$	$2t_2+1$	$2t_2$	$2t_2+1$
	p	$2s_2+1$	$2s_2$	$2s_2$	$2s_2+1$
2	$2k+1$	$4t_2+1$	$4t_2+3$	$4t_2+1$	$4t_2+3$
	$2p+1$	$4s_2+3$	$4s_2+1$	$4s_2+1$	$4s_2+3$

In the following, we will assume that the original PPT and defined by it the set of odd integers resides on the first level of presentation, while four PPTs in Table 1, derived from one PPT of the first level, correspond to the second level of presentation with a factor of four (2^2). PPTs of the next third level (partly shown in Table 2), are derived from initial PPTs of the second level, with a presentation factor of eight (2^3), and so forth.

There is a distinction between PPTs and sets of pairs of odd numbers they produce, which emerges when one begins splitting producing terms (and consequently splitting the corresponding sets). In this case, instead of operating on infinite *sets*, one could operate on the *terms* producing these sets, and in particular on PPTs, composed of two terms. Of course, the producing terms have to have certain properties, which make operations on them equivalent to desirable operations on infinite sets.

Table 2. PPTs, expressed with a factor of eight (2^3), corresponding to two initial PPTs $[4t_2 + 1, 4s_2 + 1]$ and $[4t_2 + 3, 4s_2 + 3]$ from Table 1.

	0	1	2	3	4
1	t_2 s_2	$2t_3$ $2s_3+1$	$2t_3+1$ $2s_3$	$2t_3$ $2s_3$	$2t_3+1$ $2s_3+1$
2	$4t_2+1$ $4s_2+1$	$8t_3+1$ $8s_3+5$	$8t_3+5$ $8s_3+1$	$8t_3+1$ $8s_3+1$	$8t_3+5$ $8s_3+5$
3	$4t_2+3$ $4s_2+3$	$8t_3+3$ $8s_3+7$	$8t_3+7$ $8s_3+3$	$8t_3+3$ $8s_3+3$	$8t_3+7$ $8s_3+7$

Four PPTs in Table 1 also produce a *complete set* of pairs of odd integers, same as one PPT of the first level, since we considered all possible combinations of parities of k and p . (This proposition will be strictly proved later, for now we present an *idea* of the concept.) We can continue presenting sets of pairs of odd integers by PPTs with a successively increasing factor of 2^r , using four PPTs from cells (2,1) - (2,4) in Table 1 as *initial* PPTs for the third presentation level. (Here and below the first number in brackets denotes a table's row, and the second number - a column.) Such, initial PPTs in Table 2 (column '0') for the presentation level with a factor of 2^3 are taken from Table 1, namely from cells (2,3), (2,4). Note that the power r in the presentation factor 2^r corresponds to presentation level. Furthermore, the index for variables t, s also corresponds to power r in a presentation factor. Such correspondence of this index and of the level number to power r in the presentation factor will be used throughout the paper.

Note 1: Of course, odd values of k and p could be presented as $k=2t-1$ and $p=2s-1$, in which case the subterms will be accordingly $(4t-1)$ and $(4s-1)$ instead of $(4t+3)$ and $(4s+3)$. However, since $(-\infty < t, s < \infty)$, the subterm $(4t-1)$ produces the same subset of odd integers as the subterm $(4t+3)$ does. Similarly, the subterm $(4s-1)$ produces the same subset as the subterm $(4s+3)$. So, presentations $k=2t-1$ and $k=2t+1$ are equivalent, and the same is true for $p=2s-1$ and $p=2s+1$.

2.2. Producing terms and infinite subsets of integer numbers

Although we considered PPTs, it is clear that in the same way one can consider single terms-producers (PT). Either pairs of producing terms (PPT), or single producing terms (PT), their main property is that they are *producers* of infinite sets.

Thus, for now, we can define PPT as follows. *PPT is a mathematical object, which is a producer of infinite sets of pairs of odd integers. This object has certain properties, such as an associated measure, which is defined as the ratio of the number of non-intersecting PPTs, which we choose at a given presentation level, to the total number of PPTs at this level. Measure has additivity and other properties, which will be introduced later.*

It is very important to understand that we consider PPT as an *object by itself*. PPTs are like suitcases a porter manipulates with, not knowing and not caring about their content. The only difference is that at certain transition points we may open "suitcases" to look at their content.

On the surface, one observes that the number of PPTs at each presentation level is *finite*, while they produce subsets of *infinite* number of pairs of odd integers, which could be perceived as an issue. In fact, the same issue is implicitly present in all problems, dealing with infinite sets of numbers. However, in those problems, the sets and the appropriate terms, producers of these sets, relate to one presentation level, so that one even doesn't think about such an issue, taking for granted that the expression-producer, indeed, represents an infinite set; in fact, *is* this set. For instance, if one considers an infinite set of odd integers, then a term, producing this set, is $(2k+1)$, where k is an integer. Once one proves that a certain problem has no solution for $(2k+1)$, that is for the *term*, this implicitly assumes that the problem has no solution for the *set* of all odd integers. Changing the range of k , we obtain another set.

The issue emerges when we represent the term $(2k+1)$ as a union of two subterms $(4t+1)$ and $(4t+3)$. Since k can only be odd or even, these two PTs describe all possible odd integers, the same as the initial term $(2k+1)$. Each of these terms is a producer of the associated infinite subset of odd

integers. Then, can one say that the union of these two infinite subsets represents the *whole* set of odd integers, same as the term $(2k+1)$ does? Intuitively, this is obviously so. We have two non-intersecting subsets, which together comprise *all possible* odd integers. We just have to prove that such *subsets*, indeed, are non-intersecting, and the operations of splitting them and assembling back - by appropriate splitting and assembling their producing terms - are unique and reversible. Generally, this *almost* obviousness of association of producing terms and the infinite sets they produce makes the distinction to feel subtle, and in simple cases even unnecessary. However, once we begin splitting producing terms, the things become more complicated and not so obvious. This is why we need to formalize operations with producing terms.

The uniqueness is understood as follows. Suppose subset S is produced by a term T , which then is split into several subterms t_1, t_2, \dots, t_m at another presentation level. These subterms accordingly produce subsets s_1, s_2, \dots, s_m . Then, such a splitting of the term T into subterms t_1, t_2, \dots, t_m is unique (and the appropriate operation of splitting subset S into subsets s_1, s_2, \dots, s_m , corresponding to subterms, is unique too), *if for any element in S defined by T term there is one and only one such element in one of the subsets s_1, s_2, \dots, s_m defined by the appropriate subterms t_1, t_2, \dots, t_m* . The uniqueness of the reverse operation, i. e. assembling non-intersecting subterms t_1, t_2, \dots, t_m into the term T (with appropriate assembling of non-intersecting subsets s_1, s_2, \dots, s_m into set S), can be defined similarly, that is for any element in subsets s_1, s_2, \dots, s_m defined by appropriate subterms t_1, t_2, \dots, t_m there is one and only one the same element in the set S , defined by the term T .

Operating on infinite sets, like splitting one infinite set into two, is a notoriously difficult problem. The notion of asymptotic density [1,2] uses characterization of infinite sets relative to a set of integer numbers. However, it *fundamentally* cannot serve our purpose. Indeed, by definition, asymptotic density is a *stochastic* notion, while we consider *only deterministic* values. The fact that for a certain infinite set the asymptotic density converges to value d_s does not mean that *all* elements of the set satisfy a certain criterion, say, not being a solution of some equation. Any finite number of such elements-exceptions, for which the equation has a solution, won't change the value of asymptotic density d_s , when the number of elements in the set is infinite. However, suppose we want to prove that a certain equation has no solution on a certain infinite set of integer numbers. Then, we will need *all* elements of the considered sets and subsets to satisfy the same criterion, that is to not be a solution of equation, with absolutely no possibility of exception. The notion of

asymptotic density is unsuitable for such a purpose, and *it is not used* in this proof, as some people assumed.

Instead, we introduce the notion of PPT, which allows replacing splitting and merging operations on *infinite* sets by operations on *finite* number of PPTs at each presentation level. If subterms uniquely add to a term, producing a certain set of integers, this is the same as adding corresponding subsets of integers to produce such a set. However, the operations of adding subterms have to be unique.

An illustrative analogy of PPT could be having machines of different capacity endlessly producing cookies. The same hundred of cookies per hour (c/h) can be produced either by one machine with a capacity 100 c/h, or by 20 machines with a capacity 5 c/h, or by 100 machines with a capacity 1 c/h, or by any suitable combination of machines. Even though we need *cookies*, we combine *machines*. We can do this because each machine has an associated one-to-one relationship with cookies, so that one can operate on combinations of machines instead of considering the problem in terms of endlessly produced cookies.

Similar idea underlies the notion of PPT. What we cannot do with infinite sets of pairs of odd integers directly, we can do with their representatives, or proxies, producers of these sets - PPTs, whose properties are uniquely associated with properties of infinite sets. Thus, one can also think of PPTs as more convenient for the task proxies of infinite sets, with desired specific properties.

2.3. Properties of PPTs with a factor of 2^r

Conventions: For brevity and clarity, we introduce the following conventions.

Set. It will mean a set of pairs of odd integers with no duplicates, defined (or produced) by a PPT.

Unique set. This is a set non-intersecting with the sets defined by other PPTs at the same level of presentation.

Non-intersecting PPTs. This will mean that the sets, defined by PPTs, do not intersect.

Lemma 2: *Successive presentations of odd integers with a factor of 2^r cannot contain a FC, whose module is greater or equal to 2^r .*

Proof: Presentations of odd integers with factors 2^2 and 2^3 satisfy this requirement. Let us assume that this is true for a presentation level r , that is the FC v in a term $(2^r t_r + v)$ satisfies the condition

$|v| < 2^r$. At a presentation level $(r + 1)$, this term can be presented only as $(2^{r+1}t_{r+1} + 2^r + v)$, or $(2^{r+1}t_{r+1} + v)$. In the latter term, the condition is already fulfilled. In the first term, $0 < 2^r + v < 2^r + 2^r = 2^{r+1}$, since $|v| < 2^r$ is true for level r by assumption (zero boundary corresponds to negative v). So, assuming that the condition is fulfilled at level r , we obtained that it is also fulfilled at level $(r + 1)$. According to the principle of mathematical induction, this means the validity of the assumption. This proves the Lemma.

Note 2: PPT with negative FCs can be always transformed to a PPT with positive FCs. Let parameter $v > 0$. Then one can present the first term of PPT's with negative FC as $(2^r t_r - v) = 2^r (t_r - 1) + (2^r - v) = 2^r t_{1r} + v_1$, where $t_{1r} = t_r - 1$, $v_1 = 2^r - v > 0$ (since, according to Lemma 2, $v < 2^r$). Given the obtained equality above and that $(-\infty < t_{1r}, t_r < \infty)$, both terms $(2^r t_r - v)$ and $(2^r t_{1r} + v_1)$ define the same set of odd integers. Similarly, one can convert a negative FC of the second PPT's term to a positive FC. Therefore, without restricting generality, we can consider only PPTs with positive FCs. This we assume for the rest of the paper, unless stated otherwise.

Lemma 3: *At the same presentation level r , an odd integer has a unique presentation by a PT with positive FC (let it be PT $2^r t_r + v$), that is it can be defined by only one PT with positive FC. This PT produces a set of odd integers without duplicates, such that to each value of PT's variable t_r corresponds one and only one odd integer. Such a set is unique, that is no other PT of the same level of presentation can produce the same set or any odd integer from the set.*

Proof: First we want to prove that two different PTs of the same level of presentation cannot produce the same odd integer. Let us assume that two such PTs $2^r t_{r1} + v_1$ and $2^r t_{r2} + v_2$ (for presentation levels $r \geq 1$) with different positive FCs $v_1 \neq v_2$ can produce the same odd integer for some values of $t_{1r} = t_{1r0}$ and $t_{2r} = t_{2r0}$, so that $2^r t_{1r0} + v_1 = 2^r t_{2r0} + v_2$. According to Lemma 2, $v_1 < 2^r$, $v_2 < 2^r$. We can rewrite the equation as $t_{1r0} - t_{2r0} = (v_2 - v_1)/2^r$. Since both FCs are positive, $|v_1 - v_2| < 2^r$. Then, since $v_1 \neq v_2$, the right part is rational, which is impossible, because the left part is an integer or zero. So, our assumption is invalid, and each odd integer number at the same level of presentation can be defined by one PT only.

Let us prove that one PT (let it be PT $2^r t_r + v$) defines a unique set of odd integers at this level of presentation, and that this set has no duplicate values (provided the variable t_r has no duplicates, which was earlier stated). For one value of t_r , this PT produces one odd integer only, since the formula $2^r t_r + v$ presents a one-to-one relationship between its variable t_r and the output set of integers. The opposite is also true, that is to each output integer corresponds only one value of t_r . Suppose, there are such different integers t_{r1} and t_{r2} , which produce the same odd integer, and $t_{r1} \neq t_{r2}$. Then, $2^r t_{r1} + v = 2^r t_{r2} + v$, from which follows $t_{r1} = t_{r2}$, contrary to the assumption. So, the term $2^r t_r + v$ cannot produce the same odd integer for different values of t_r . Thus, we found that for one value of t_r there is *one and only one* output odd integer.

Since t_r has no duplicate values, the set of odd integers, produced by PT $2^r t_r + v$, also has no duplicates. On the other hand, we already proved that at the same level of presentation each odd integer can be defined by one PT only, so that any odd integer in the produced by PT set can be defined by only this PT, and by no other. Therefore, each PT of the same level of presentation defines a unique set of odd integers, which does not intersect with the sets of odd integers defined by other PTs of this level of presentation, and this set has no duplicates.

This proves the Lemma.

Lemma 4: Consider four PPTs at the same level of presentation, derived from one initial PPT of the previous level. The set of pairs of odd integers, defined by the initial PPT, has no duplicates. Then, each derived PPT defines a unique set at this level, with no duplicates.

Proof: Four derived PPTs correspond to *all* possible combinations of parities of parameters (t_r, s_r) , which are defined as combinations of parities in Table 2 (row 1, columns 1-4). Four derived PPTs of level $r+1$ are as follows: (1) $[2^{r+1} t_{r+1} + v, 2^{r+1} s_{r+1} + 2^r + w]$, (2) $[2^{r+1} t_{r+1} + 2^r + v, 2^{r+1} s_{r+1} + w]$, (3) $[2^{r+1} t_{r+1} + v, 2^{r+1} s_{r+1} + w]$, (4) $[2^{r+1} t_{r+1} + 2^r + v, 2^{r+1} s_{r+1} + 2^r + w]$. Let values $t_{r+1,1}$ and $s_{r+1,1}$ correspond to one PPT, and $t_{r+1,2}$ and $s_{r+1,2}$ correspond to another PPT. Let us find the difference of PTs located in the first position in the above PPTs, and the difference of PTs located in the second position. In total, we have six pairs of such differences.

1. $[2^{r+1}(t_{r+1,1} - t_{r+1,2}) - 2^r, 2^{r+1}(s_{r+1,1} - s_{r+1,2}) + 2^r]$ (difference of PTs of PPTs 1 and 2)
2. $[2^{r+1}(t_{r+1,1} - t_{r+1,2}), 2^{r+1}(s_{r+1,1} - s_{r+1,2}) + 2^r]$ (difference of PTs of PPTs 1 and 3)

3. $[2^{r+1}(t_{r+1,1} - t_{r+1,2}) - 2^r, 2^{r+1}(s_{r+1,1} - s_{r+1,2})]$ (difference of PTs of PPTs 1 and 4)
4. $[2^{r+1}(t_{r+1,1} - t_{r+1,2}) + 2^r, 2^{r+1}(s_{r+1,1} - s_{r+1,2})]$ (difference of PTs of PPTs 2 and 3)
5. $[2^{r+1}(t_{r+1,1} - t_{r+1,2}), 2^{r+1}(s_{r+1,1} - s_{r+1,2}) - 2^r]$ (difference of PTs of PPTs 2 and 4)
6. $[2^{r+1}(t_{r+1,1} - t_{r+1,2}) - 2^r, 2^{r+1}(s_{r+1,1} - s_{r+1,2}) - 2^r]$ (difference of PTs of PPTs 3 and 4)

If we can prove that in these pairs two terms can be simultaneously equal to zero, this will mean that the corresponding to these differences PPTs can produce the same pair of odd integers.

For the first pair of differences we would accordingly have two equations:

$2^{r+1}(t_{r+1,1} - t_{r+1,2}) - 2^r = 0$, $2^{r+1}(s_{r+1,1} - s_{r+1,2}) + 2^r = 0$, which can be transformed to the following: $(t_{r+1,1} - t_{r+1,2}) = 1/2$, $(s_{r+1,1} - s_{r+1,2}) = -1/2$. The left part of these equations is an integer or zero, while the right parts present a rational number, which is impossible. So, these two PPTs cannot produce the same pairs of odd integers.

For the second pair of differences, we will accordingly have equations $2^{r+1}(t_{r+1,1} - t_{r+1,2}) = 0$, $2^{r+1}(s_{r+1,1} - s_{r+1,2}) + 2^r = 0$. The first equation has a solution, while the second one can be transformed to $(s_{r+1,1} - s_{r+1,2}) = -1/2$, which has no solution for the same reasons as equations for the first pair of differences.

Similarly we can consider differences 3-6 to find out that their terms cannot be simultaneously equal to zero too. Thus, all four derived PPTs of level $(r+1)$ produce unique sets of pairs of odd integers. Since PTs composing PPTs are unique and have no duplicates, the sets produced by PPTs also have no duplicates.

This proves the Lemma.

Note 3: For successive *complete* presentations of all PPTs at each level, the number of PPTs increases in a geometrical progression with a common ratio of *four*, since each initial PPT produces *four* new PPTs at the next presentation level. (Each new PPT corresponds to one of the four possible parity combinations of input variable, like t_2 , s_2 in Table 2, whose parity is expressed through t_3 , s_3 .) Such, at the second level, we have four PPTs ($P_2 = 4^1$, where P is the number of PPTs). At the third presentation level, the total number of PPTs is $P_3 = 4^2$. Thus, the number of PPTs at level r can be assumed equal to $P_r = 4^{r-1}$. Suppose that this generalization is true for level r . Then, the number

of PPTs at level $(r + 1)$ increases by four-fold, that is $P_{r+1} = 4^r$. According to principle of mathematical induction, this means that the formula $P_r = 4^{r-1}$, indeed, is correct.

Lemma 5: Consider one initial PPT at an arbitrary presentation level $r \geq 1$, which produces four PPTs at the next presentation level $(r + 1)$. Then, for any pair of odd integers in the set, produced by initial PPT at level r , there is one and only one the same pair at level $(r + 1)$ in one of the four sets produced by four derived PPTs. The sets defined by one PPT at level r , and by four PPTs at level $(r + 1)$, are the same.

Proof: We do not impose any limitations on the value of r other than $r \geq 1$, so that r can be an arbitrary big number, to infinity. PPTs of the next presentation level $(r+1)$ are obtained by branching each initial PPT of the form of $[2^r t_r + v, 2^r s_r + w]$ from level r into *all* four possible combinations of parities of variables (t_r, s_r) . These parity combinations are defined similarly to combinations of parities in Table 2 (row 1, columns 1-4). Parity combinations and corresponding PPTs, obtained at level $r + 1$ this way, are as follows:

<i>Parity</i>	<i>PPT</i>
1. $[2t_{r+1}, 2s_{r+1} + 1]$	$[2^{r+1}t_{r+1} + v, 2^{r+1}s_{r+1} + 2^r + w]$
2. $[2t_{r+1} + 1, 2s_{r+1}]$	$[2^{r+1}t_{r+1} + 2^r + v, 2^{r+1}s_{r+1} + w]$
3. $[2t_{r+1}, 2s_{r+1}]$	$[2^{r+1}t_{r+1} + v, 2^{r+1}s_{r+1} + w]$
4. $[2t_{r+1} + 1, 2s_{r+1} + 1]$	$[2^{r+1}t_{r+1} + 2^r + v, 2^{r+1}s_{r+1} + 2^r + w]$

Let us show that for any pair B of odd integers, defined by an initial PPT at level r as $[2^r t_{r0} + v, 2^r s_{r0} + w]$, there is *one and only one* such pair at level $(r + 1)$. Here, (t_{r0}, s_{r0}) are concrete integers defining the pair B . Parity of (t_{r0}, s_{r0}) can correspond to only one of the four possible parity combinations 1- 4 above, and not to any other, since there are no other parity combinations. For instance, let it be combination 1, that is $(t_{r0} = 2t_{r+1,0}, s_{r0} = 2s_{r+1,0} + 1)$, where index '0' denotes that this is a concrete integer. Using this substitution, we find

$$2^r t_{r0} + v = 2^{r+1} t_{r+1,0} + v; \quad 2^r s_{r0} + w = 2^{r+1} s_{r+1,0} + 2^r + w.$$

So, at level $r + 1$, the corresponding to this combination of parities PPT (let call it PPT 1) produces the same pair of odd integers B , defined as follows: $[2^{r+1} t_{r+1,0} + v, 2^{r+1} s_{r+1,0} + 2^r + w]$. Thus, we

found that such a pair of odd integers at level $(r + 1)$ exists. (This existence is supported by the following consideration. Since variables (t_{r+1}, s_{r+1}) are defined on the range $(-\infty, \infty)$, they can take values $(t_{r+1,0}, s_{r+1,0})$). According to Lemma 4, this pair has no duplicate in the set defined by PPT 1 of level $(r + 1)$. Also, according to the same Lemma, this PPT defines a unique set of pairs of odd integers at level $r + 1$ (among the sets produced by four derived PPTs), so that, indeed, three other PPTs cannot define pair B at this level.

Similarly, we can consider parity combinations 2-4 of variables (t_{r0}, s_{r0}) , whose appropriate PPTs produce the same and the only pair of odd integers, as the initial PPT does.

Let us show that the same is true in the opposite direction, that is a pair of odd integers B at level $(r + 1)$ corresponds to only one the same pair at level r . Suppose such pair B is produced by one of four PPTs, for the concrete values of variables $(t_{r+1,0}, s_{r+1,0})$. For certainty, we assume that this pair is produced by a PPT, corresponding to parity combination 2 (PPT 2), so that the pair of odd integers B is $(2^{r+1}t_{r+1,0} + 2^r + v, 2^{r+1}s_{r+1,0} + w)$. The pair's terms can be transformed as follows:

$$2^{r+1}t_{r+1,0} + 2^r + v = 2^r(2t_{r+1,0} + 1) + v = 2^rt_{r0} + v; \quad 2^{r+1}s_{r+1,0} + w = 2^r(2s_{r+1,0}) + w = 2^rs_{r0} + w,$$

where $t_{r0} = (2t_{r+1,0} + 1)$, $s_{r0} = 2s_{r+1,0}$.

So, we obtained the presentation of the same pair B at level r as $(2^rt_{r0} + v, 2^rs_{r0} + w)$. This pair B at level r exists, since the range of variables (t_r, s_r) is by definition $(-\infty, \infty)$, and consequently includes values (t_{r0}, s_{r0}) . Pair B has no duplicates at level r for the following reasons.

- (a) We used one-to-one transformation (such as one-to-one substitutions to find values (t_{r0}, s_{r0}) in transformation formulas) to transform pair B from level $(r + 1)$ to level r , so that for one pair of input values $(t_{r+1,0}, s_{r+1,0})$ in PPT 2 at level $(r + 1)$ there is only one pair (t_{r0}, s_{r0}) of variables (t_r, s_r) at level r ;
- (b) According to Lemma 4, PPT 2 produces a set of pairs that has no duplicates. Consequently, there is only one pair B in this set;
- (c) The set, produced by PPT 2, is unique among the sets produced by four derived PPTs, according to Lemma 4, so that none of the remaining three PPTs can produce a set containing the pair B , but only PPT 2.

Consequently, there can be only one such transformed pair B at level r .

Similarly, we can consider conversion of PPTs, corresponding to parity combinations 1, 3 and 4, to find out that for each pair of odd integers from the sets, defined by these PPTs, there is only one such pair in the set, defined by the initial PPT at level r .

So, we found that in case of four PPTs, produced at level $(r+1)$ from one initial PPT of the previous level r , there is one-to-one transformation of pairs of odd integers from level r to level $(r+1)$, and also in the opposite direction from level $(r+1)$ to level r . This means that any pair of odd integers at presentation level r corresponds to *one and only one* the same pair at level $(r+1)$. In turn, this means that the sets, defined by one PPT at level r , and by four PPTs at level $(r+1)$, are *the same*. If this was not so, then a pair of odd integers would exist at one level, that has no presentation at the other level. However, we have just shown that this is not so.

Using the found above bidirectional inclusion of the sets, defined by the initial and by four derived PPTs, we can formulate the result as follows. Let us denote the set defined by i -th PPT at level r as $s_{r,i}$, where the first index denotes the presentation level, and the second index i denotes the PPT's ordeal number at this level. We denote the sets defined by j -th derived PPTs at level $(r+1)$ (derived from i -th initial PPT of level r) accordingly as $s_{r+1,ij}$. Then, the found above bidirectional

inclusion of sets can be presented in the notations of set theory as $s_{r,i} \subseteq \bigcup_{j=1}^{j=4} s_{r+1,ij}$, $\bigcup_{j=1}^{j=4} s_{r+1,ij} \subseteq s_{r,i}$, from

which follows, according to properties of sets, equality of sets.

$$s_{r,i} = \bigcup_{j=1}^{j=4} s_{r+1,ij} \tag{2}$$

This completes the proof of the Lemma.

For the following, we will need to prove that successive presentations with a factor of 2^r , beginning from the first level, produce the whole set of pairs of odd integers when transformed to the next level, and that this presentation is unique - that is for each pair of odd integers at one level there is one and only one such pair at any other presentation level. Besides, we also need to prove that a similar unambiguous transformation is possible for a group of PPTs at any arbitrary level.

Lemma 6: *Let all or several PPTs of level $r \geq 1$ to be transformed sequentially to each next level. Then thus obtained PPTs at each next level produce unique sets with no duplicates. Together such PPTs of each level produce the same set as the set produced by all original PPTs at level r , such that for any pair of odd integers from the set produced by the original PPTs there is one and only one the same pair at any other presentation level.*

Proof: Part 1. (Complete set of PPTs). We begin from PPT of the first level of presentation $[(2k+1), (2p+1)]$, which defines the *whole set of pairs of odd integers* (let denote it as W) with no duplicates (see the beginning of subsection 2.1). Lemmas 4 and 5 are directly applicable to the first and second levels, which accordingly have one and four PPTs. Then, according to Lemma 4, four PPTs of the second level produce unique sets with no duplicates. According to Lemma 5, the union of these four sets produces the same set, as initial PPT of the first level, that is also the *whole set* W . For any pair of odd integers in the set, produced by PPT of the first level, there is one and only one the same pair in the total set produced by four PPTs of the second level (Lemma 5).

Now we will use four PPTs of the second level as initial PPTs for the third level. Fig. 1 illustrates the idea graphically for the second and the third presentation levels, while Fig. 2 - for two arbitrary adjacent levels r and $(r + 1)$.

Fig. 1. PPTs of presentation level 2, and derived from them groups of four PPTs at level 3.

Each of four initial PPT from level two produces four PPTs at the third level, so that we have four such groups of PPTs. According to Lemma 5, each such group of four PPTs produces the same set as its initial PPT. Initial PPTs of the third level are PPTs of the second level, each of which produces a unique set with no duplicates, and together four PPTs of the second level produce the whole set of pairs of odd integers W . So, each of four groups of PPTs at level three also produces a unique set with no duplicates (that is the same set as its initial PPT taken from the second level), while the union of these group sets defines the whole set W - same as the union of sets produced by four PPTs at level two. Thus, using (2) and its notations, we can write

$$\bigcup_{i=1}^{i=4} s_{2,i} = \bigcup_{j=1}^{j=4} S_{3,j}, \text{ where } S_{3,j} = \bigcup_{k=1}^{k=4} s_{3,jk}$$

Note that at both the second and the third levels we considered *all* PPTs of these levels. In the following, we will call the set of all PPTs of one level a *complete set of PPTs*. As we have seen for levels 1 - 3, their complete sets of PPTs define the whole set of pairs of odd integers W .

According to Lemma 4, PPTs inside each group of four derived PPTs produce unique sets with no duplicates. Since each group of PPTs, in turn, produces a unique set, this means that *all* PPTs of the third level produce unique sets with no duplicates.

Fig. 2. PPTs of presentation level r , and derived from them groups of four PPTs at level $(r + 1)$.

Let us consider an arbitrary presentation level $r \geq 1$. According to Note 3, the total number of PPTs T at level r is $T = 4^{r-1}$ (see Fig. 2). These PPTs compose a complete set of PPTs. Let us assume that the same initial arrangement, as for levels two and three, is valid for this level. This means that all T PPTs at level r produce unique sets of pairs of odd integers with no duplicates, while the union of these sets produces the whole set W . Each PPT of level r is used as an initial PPT for a group of four derived PPTs at level $(r+1)$. Let us show that the latter groups of PPTs together constitute a complete set of PPTs. Indeed, PPTs of level $(r+1)$ can be derived only by using initial PPTs (which are PPTs of the previous level), and we use *all* possible initial PPTs. Each group of four PPTs produces the same set, as its initial PPT, according to Lemma 5. By assumption, the sets produced by T initial PPTs, are unique and have no duplicates, while together they produce the set W . Consequently, the sets produced by T groups of PPTs are also unique, have no duplicates, and their union also produces the set W . Using notions analogous to formula (2), we can write:

$$\bigcup_{i=1}^{i=T} s_{r,i} = \bigcup_{j=1}^{j=T} S_{r+1,j}, \text{ where } S_{r+1,j} = \bigcup_{k=1}^{k=4} s_{r+1,jk} \quad (3)$$

Inside each group, PPTs also produce unique sets with no duplicates, according to Lemma 4. Since each group of four derived PPTs produces a unique set too, this means that *all* $4 \times T$ PPTs at level $(r+1)$ produce unique sets with no duplicates.

So, we found that first three presentation levels are composed of complete sets of PPTs, which define the whole set W at each level. We assumed that PPTs of an arbitrary presentation level r also present a complete set of PPTs with no duplicates. Based on this assumption, we obtained that derived PPTs of level $(r + 1)$ also have the same properties: (a) they present a complete set of PPTs; (b) each PPT defines a set unique at this level, with no duplicates; (c) complete set of PPTs of each level defines the whole set of pairs of odd integers W . According to principle of mathematical

induction, this means that any arbitrary level of presentation $r \geq 1$ has the same properties. Since the obtained result is valid for $r \geq 1$, there is no upper boundary for r , and so the same arrangement remains true when r goes to infinity.

So, we proved that a complete set of PPTs of each level, beginning from the first one, when transformed to the next level also defines a complete set of PPTs. These complete sets of PPTs of each level define the whole set W with no duplicates. This means that for any pair of odd integers B at one level of presentation there is *one and only one* the same pair B at any other presentation level. We also proved that each PPT of one level defines a unique set with no duplicates.

Part 2. (Partial set of PPTs at an arbitrary presentation level.) Now we will consider the case of transformation of part of PPTs of an arbitrary level r to the next levels. We proved above that PPTs of any level produce unique sets with no duplicates at this level, when we considered complete sets of PPTs. If we take M of these PPTs (less than a complete set of PPTs), they also produce unique sets $s_{r,j}$ ($j=1, \dots, M$) with no duplicates. Let us assume that the union of these sets produces set

$S_r = \bigcup_{j=1}^{j=M} s_{r,j}$. When transformed to the next presentation level, each of M PPTs, considered as an initial PPT for level $(r + 1)$, produces a group of four derived PPTs, so that the total number of derived PPTs at level $(r + 1)$ is $4M$. According to Lemma 5, each such group produces the same set as its initial PPT, so that the groups' sets are also unique and have no duplicates at level $(r+1)$. If we denote the set corresponding to j -th group as $S_{r+1,j}$, then we can write $S_{r+1,j} = s_{r,j}$. In turn,

$S_{r+1,j} = \bigcup_{k=1}^{k=4} s_{r+1,jk}$, where $s_{r+1,jk}$ is the k -th set produced by k -th PPT in j -th group at level $(r+1)$ (this group corresponds to j -th initial PPT from level r). Sets $s_{r,j}$ at level r are unique and do not intersect. So, the sets $S_{r+1,j}$ are also unique and do not intersect. Consequently, the union S_{r+1} of non-intersecting sets, produced by M groups, presents the same set as the union S_r at level r , that is $S_{r+1} = S_r$. So, we can write an equality similar to (3).

$$\bigcup_{i=1}^{i=M} s_{r,i} = \bigcup_{j=1}^{j=M} S_{r+1,j}, \text{ where } S_{r+1,j} = \bigcup_{k=1}^{k=4} s_{r+1,jk} \quad (4)$$

In addition, each PPT within such a group of four derived PPTs defines a unique set with no duplicates (Lemma 4). Since the groups' sets do not intersect and have no duplicates, this means that *all* derived $4M$ PPTs at level $(r+1)$ produce unique sets with no duplicates. (The same result immediately follows from Part 1 of the proof for complete sets of PPTs, which proved that *all* PPTs of the same level produce unique sets with no duplicates.)

Let us generalize the obtained results. Suppose we did L such transformation steps. We assume that $S_{r+L} = S_{r+L-1}$. Since with each next level the number of PPTs increases by four-fold (see Note 3), if M is the number of PPTs at level r , we will have $4^L M$ PPTs at level $(r+L)$, which will be used as initial PPTs for level $(r+L+1)$. According to Part 1 of this proof, all $4^L M$ PPTs at level $(r+L)$ produce unique sets with no duplicates. The $4^L M$ groups of four PPTs at level $(r+L+1)$, derived from the corresponding $4^L M$ PPTs of level $(r+L)$, according to Lemma 5 produce at level $(r+L+1)$ the same non-intersecting sets with no duplicates as their initial PPTs. Thus, the union of $4^L M$ group sets at level $(r+L+1)$ produces the same set as the union of all $4^L M$ PPTs at level $(r+L)$, that is

$$\bigcup_{i=1}^{i=4^L M} S_{r+L,i} = \bigcup_{j=1}^{j=4^L M} S_{r+L+1,j}, \text{ where } S_{r+L+1,j} = \bigcup_{k=1}^{k=4} S_{r+L+1,jk}$$

So, we obtained that $S_{r+L+1} = S_{r+L}$. In addition, according to Part 1 of this proof, all $4 \times 4^L M = 4^{L+1} M$ derived PPTs of level $(r+L+1)$ produce unique sets with no duplicates.

So, first we found that PPTs of levels r and $(r+1)$ satisfy the conditions of Lemma, that is the original PPTs of level r together produce the same set as transformed PPTs of level $(r+1)$, while all derived PPTs of level $(r+1)$ produce unique sets with no duplicates. Then we showed that the same is true for an arbitrary level $(r+L)$, assuming that PPTs of this level, derived sequentially from PPTs of level r till level $(r+L)$, produce the same set of pairs of odd integers as the original PPTs of level r . According to principle of mathematical induction, this means that in case of partial selection of PPTs from an arbitrary level, the Lemma is fulfilled too. In particular, we proved that $S_{r+L+1} = S_{r+L} = \dots = S_{r+1} = S_r$.

One-to-one correspondence of pairs of odd integers at different presentation levels.

In Part 1, we proved that complete sets of PPTs at each level, beginning from the first one, define the whole set of pairs of odd integers W with no duplicates. This means that for any pair of odd integers B at one level of presentation there is *one and only one* the same pair B at any other presentation level. In case of Part 2, which considered partial selection of PPTs at an arbitrary level, the same assertion stays true for the following reasons. We proved that the transformed PPTs of each level produce the same original set of pairs of odd integers S_r with no duplicates. Suppose we have one pair of odd integers B at one level. Then, since the sets corresponding to other presentation levels are the same, pair B exists in the sets defined by transformed PPTs of other levels, and this

pair has no duplicates at a chosen level. Thus, to any pair B of odd integers at one level corresponds *one and only one* the same pair in the set defined by transformed PPTs of other level.

This completes the proof of Lemma.

Corollary 1: *At any presentation level $r \geq 1$, for any pair of odd integers there is one and only one PPT of this level which defines this pair, and this pair has no duplicates at this level.*

Proof: According to Lemma 6, the complete set of PPTs of one level defines a whole set of pairs of odd integers. This means that for any pair of odd integers B , at any level of presentation, exists PPT defining this pair. According to the same Lemma 6, such a PPT defines a set with no duplicates, while this set does not intersect with the sets defined by other PPTs of this level. Thus only one such pair B exists in the set defined by a complete set of PPTs of this level.

So, we found that, on one hand, at any level of presentation any pair of odd integers is necessarily presented by some PPT. On the other hand, there can be only one such PPT, and this PPT produces a unique set of pairs of odd integers with no duplicates. Thus, at any level of presentation, any pair of odd integers B can be defined by *one and only one* PPT, and this pair has no duplicates at this level.

This proves the Corollary.

Distribution of PPTs and associated sets across presentation levels.

It was proved in Lemma 6 that the set produced by original PPTs is the same as the set produced by PPTs sequentially derived from the original PPTs. Using this property, we can distribute the set of PPTs of one level across different upper levels. Accordingly, the sets initially associated with PPTs of one level, will be also distributed across different levels. The following Lemma describes properties of distributed PPTs (and of associated with them sets of pairs of odd integers).

Lemma 7: *(Distribution of PPTs) PPTs of one level can be distributed across subsequent presentation levels in such a way that half of PPTs remains associated with the original level, while the other half of PPTs is used as initial PPTs for the next level, and is thus transferred to this level. Then such a procedure of splitting transferred PPTs at each next level by half and transferring one half of PPTs to the next level is repeated either until a final presentation level, or to infinity. The set corresponding to distributed PPTs is the same as the set defined by original PPTs. Each distributed PPT produces a unique (among all distributed PPTs) set with no duplicates.*

First we consider such distribution for a complete set of PPTs, beginning from the second level (Fig. 3). Then, we will generalize the obtained results for an incomplete set of PPTs and an arbitrary beginning level.

Proof: Part 1. Distribution of PPTs from the second level (distribution of complete sets of PPTs).

The complete set of four PPTs of the second level, derived from one PPT of the first level, according to Lemma 6 produces a whole set of pairs of odd integers W . These four PPTs are shown in Table 1 and in Fig. 3. Each PPT produces a unique set (Lemma 6). We split these four PPTs into two groups, each containing two PPTs; for instance, PPTs $[4t_2 + 1, 4s_2 + 3]$ and $[4t_2 + 3, 4s_2 + 1]$ (in bold in Table 1) form the first group (columns 1 and 2), and PPTs $[4t_2 + 1, 4s_2 + 1]$ and $[4t_2 + 3, 4s_2 + 3]$ (columns 3 and 4) form the second group. PPTs of the first group (grey boxes in Fig. 3) are left at the second level, while PPTs of the second group (white boxes) are used as two initial PPTs for the third level. This way, these two initial PPTs are transformed into eight PPTs of the third level (Table 2 and Fig. 3).

Each group of four derived PPTs at level three (in Table 2 in rows 2 and 3 accordingly) produces *the same* set, as its initial PPTs $[4t_2 + 1, 4s_2 + 1]$ and $[4t_2 + 3, 4s_2 + 3]$. Since initial PPTs produce unique sets with no duplicates, the sets produced by groups are also unique and have no duplicates. According to Lemma 5, the sets within each group are unique and have no duplicates. Consequently, all eight derived PPTs at level three produce unique sets with no duplicates (the same result also directly follows from Lemma 6, which states that PPTs of one level define unique sets with no duplicates). Formula (3) will be rewritten for this case as follows.

$$\bigcup_{i=3}^{i=4} s_{2,i} = \bigcup_{j=1}^{j=2} S_{3,j}, \text{ where } S_{3,j} = \bigcup_{k=1}^{k=4} s_{3,jk} \quad (5)$$

Fig. 3. Distribution of PPTs across sequential presentation levels. Grey boxes correspond to PPTs, which remain associated with the current level. White boxes correspond to PPTs that are used as initial PPTs for the next presentation level, and thus are transferred to that level.

Now the set of pairs of odd integers, produced by a complete set of four PPTs of the second level, is defined by two PPTs in cells (2,1), (2,2) of Table 1, left on the second level, and by eight PPTs of the third level in Table 2, derived from two PPTs of the second level in cells (2,3), (2,4), that is

$$\bigcup_{i=1}^{i=4} s_{2,i} = \left(\bigcup_{i=1}^{i=2} s_{2,i} \right) \cup \left(\bigcup_{j=1}^{j=2} s_{3,j} \right), \text{ where } s_{3,j} = \bigcup_{k=1}^{k=4} s_{3,jk} \quad (6)$$

Whole set of pairs of odd integers W. Since the second level contains a complete set of PPTs, and consequently defines the whole set of pairs of odd integers W (Lemma 6), the set produced by the union in (6) also defines the set W .

Uniqueness of distributed sets. PPTs 1-4 of the second level, of which PPTs 1 and 2 are left at the second level (Fig. 3), and PPTs 3 and 4 are transformed to the third level, produce unique sets with no duplicates (Lemma 5). The sets defined by PPTs 3 and 4 of the second level were transformed into eight PPTs of the third level, which together define the same set as PPTs 3 and 4. Each of eight PPTs of level three defines a unique set with no duplicates (Lemma 6). Thus, effectively we have done an equivalent substitution of unique sets defined by PPTs 3 and 4 of the second level by unique sets defined by PPTs 1-8 of the third level. (All aforementioned sets have no duplicates.) Thus, PPTs distributed through levels two and three produce unique sets with no duplicates.

Now we can continue the splitting operation for PPTs of the third level, leaving four PPTs at the third level (for illustration, these four PPTs in Table 2 are in bold), while using the other four PPTs (in a regular font in Table 2) as initial PPTs for the fourth level, which will produce sixteen PPTs at this level (Fig. 3). According to Lemma 6, sixteen derived PPTs of level four produce the same set as their four initial PPTs. Thus, the original set produced by four PPTs of the second level, will be defined by two PPTs of the second level, by four PPTs of the third level, and by sixteen PPTs of the fourth level. Note that it does not matter, which particular four PPTs from the previous level to choose to transfer to the fourth level (since all of them produce non-intersecting sets with no duplicates), unless one needs PPTs with certain properties - for instance, PPTs with equal FCs. In the last case, we should choose PPTs from columns 3 and 4 in Table 2 and transfer them to the fourth level as initial PPTs. Then the union of appropriate sets will be as follows.

$$\bigcup_{i=1}^{i=4} S_{2,i} = \left(\bigcup_{i=1}^{i=2} S_{2,i} \right) \cup \left(\bigcup_{j=1}^{j=2} S_{3h,j} \right) \cup \left(\bigcup_{j=1}^{j=4} S_{4,j} \right), \text{ where } S_{3h,j} = \bigcup_{k=1}^{k=2} S_{3,jk}, S_{4,j} = \bigcup_{k=1}^{k=4} S_{4,jk} \quad (7)$$

Here, at the third level, each set $S_{3h,j}$ is produced by *two* first PPTs from each group of *four* PPTs (in Table 2, we have two such groups - in rows 2 and 3). Two such PPTs of each group together produce one set $S_{3h,j}$: the set $S_{3h,1}$ is produced by PPTs left at the third level in cells (2,1), (2,2), and the set $S_{3h,2}$ is produced by PPTs left in cells (3,1), (3,2). (Note that we could equally leave PPTs 1-4 at the third level, and transfer PPTs 5-8 to the fourth level.)

Uniqueness of distributed sets. PPTs 1-8 of level three define unique sets with no duplicates (Lemma 6). From them, PPTs 1,2,5,6 (Fig. 3) were left at the third level; PPTs 3,4,7,8 were transformed to sixteen PPTs of level four. These sixteen PPTs (a) define unique sets with no duplicates (Lemma 6); (b) define the same set as their initial PPTs 3,4,7,8 of the third level. Thus, effectively we did an equivalent substitution of unique sets defined by PPTs 3,4,7,8 of level three by the sets defined by unique sixteen PPTs of level four, so that the resulting set defined by all distributed PPTs remained the same, and all distributed PPTs, this time till level four, define unique sets, which have no duplicates.

The whole set W. Since the resulting set, defined by PPTs distributed till level four remains the same, it also represents the whole set W (this is also what equality (7) shows).

Alternatively, we can leave at the third level four PPTs of one group corresponding, for instance, PPTs in row 2 in Table 2 (which produce set $S_{3,1}$), while using four PPTs of the other group (in row 3 in Table 2, producing set $S_{3,2}$) as initial PPTs for level four. In this case, (7) will be rewritten as follows.

$$\bigcup_{i=1}^{i=4} s_{2,i} = \left(\bigcup_{i=1}^{i=2} s_{2,i} \right) \cup (S_{3,1}) \cup \left(\bigcup_{j=1}^{j=4} S_{4,j} \right), \text{ where } S_{4,j} = \bigcup_{k=1}^{k=4} s_{4,jk} \quad (8)$$

Note that although $S_{4,j}$ in (7) and (8) look the same, they are based on different initial PPTs. Distributed PPTs in this case also produce unique sets with no duplicates, which can be proved using the same considerations earlier applied to the union of sets (7).

For our purposes, we will use presentation (7), when two PPTs of *each* group of four PPTs, corresponding to one initial PPT, are left at the current level, while two other PPTs of the same groups are used as initial PPTs for the next level.

We can continue splitting these sixteen PPTs of the fourth level into two equal groups of eight PPTs each, leaving one group at level four, and use eight PPTs of the other group as initial PPTs for level five, which will accordingly produce 32 PPTs at this level. In accordance with Lemma 6, the sets produced by eight initial PPTs from level four, and by 32 PPTs of level five, are the same. Thus, now the original set of pairs, produced by PPTs of the second level, will be presented by two PPTs of the second level, by four PPTs of the third level, by eight PPTs of the fourth level, and by 32 PPTs of the fifth level. The last PPTs can be again divided into two equal groups, to which the same operations as above can be applied, and so forth, to infinity, since level r is not limited. So, with the fifth presentation level, we obtain the following union of sets, which is equal to the union of original sets of the second level.

$$\bigcup_{i=1}^{i=4} s_{2,i} = \left(\bigcup_{i=1}^{i=2} s_{2,i} \right) \cup \left(\bigcup_{j=1}^{j=2} S_{3h,j} \right) \cup \left(\bigcup_{j=1}^{j=4} S_{4h,j} \right) \cup \left(\bigcup_{j=1}^{j=8} S_{5,j} \right) \quad (9)$$

$$\text{where } S_{3h,j} = \bigcup_{k=1}^{k=2} s_{3,jk}, \quad S_{4h,j} = \bigcup_{k=1}^{k=2} s_{4,jk}, \quad S_{5,j} = \bigcup_{k=1}^{k=4} s_{5,jk}$$

Uniqueness of distributed sets. This time, we have an equivalent substitution of unique sets defined by eight transformed PPTs of level four by 32 unique sets produced by PPTs of level five, derived from those transformed eight PPTs. (According to Lemma 6, the sets produced by those eight and 32 PPTs are the same). All these sets have no duplicates.

The whole set W. Due to equivalency of the above substitution, it does not change the resulting set produced by PPTs distributed till level five compared to distribution till level four. The last distribution produces a whole set W . So, the PPTs distributed till level five together also produce a whole set W . The same assertion also follows from equality (9), since the union in the left part presents the set defined by four PPTs of the second level, which is the whole set W .

We can generalize the obtained results using method of mathematical induction, assuming the following. The number of initial PPTs at level r , based on observed relationships, is equal to 2^{r-2} (at the second level we have one PPT, at the third level - two PPTs, at the fourth level - four PPTs, at the fifth level - eight PPTs). In this formula, $r \geq 2$ (we have no initial PPTs for the first level). Accordingly, the number of PPTs produced by initial PPTs at level r is $4 \times 2^{r-2} = 2^r$, from which a half $2^r / 2 = 2^{r-1}$ remains at level r , while the other half is transferred to the next level $(r+1)$. If this is the final level of distribution, then the number of distributed PPTs at level r will be 2^r . The entire original set of pairs of odd integers W of the second level is reproduced by the union of sets defined by PPTs sequentially distributed across presentation levels from two to r . Distributed PPTs produce unique sets with no duplicates.

So, if one stops distribution at level r , the number of the appropriate distributed PPTs at each level, beginning from the second one, is $[2, 4, \dots, 2^{r-2}, 2^r]$. Since we do not have limitation on the upper boundary of r , such a distribution can go to infinity. In this case, the number of PPTs, beginning from the second level, is $[2, 4, \dots, 2^{r-2}, 2^{r-1}, \dots]$, presenting a geometrical progression with a common ratio of two. The appropriate set, produced by distributed PPTs, based on these formulas, will be defined for the finite number of presentation levels as follows.

$$\bigcup_{i=1}^{i=4} S_{2,i} = \left(\bigcup_{i=1}^{i=2} S_{2,i} \right) \cup \left(\bigcup_{j=1}^{j=2} S_{3h,j} \right) \cup \left(\bigcup_{j=1}^{j=4} S_{4h,j} \right) \cup \left(\bigcup_{j=1}^{j=8} S_{5h,j} \right) \cup \dots \cup \left(\bigcup_{j=1}^{j=2^{r-3}} S_{(r-1)h,j} \right) \cup \left(\bigcup_{j=1}^{j=2^{r-2}} S_{r,j} \right) \quad (10)$$

$$\text{where } S_{mh,j} = \bigcup_{k=1}^{k=2} S_{m,jk}, \quad 3 \leq m \leq r-1; \quad S_{r,j} = \bigcup_{k=1}^{k=4} S_{r,jk}.$$

For the infinite number of distribution levels, the derived PPTs of all levels are divided into two equal groups, so that (10) transforms into

$$\bigcup_{i=1}^{i=4} S_{2,i} = \left(\bigcup_{i=1}^{i=2} S_{2,i} \right) \cup \left(\bigcup_{j=1}^{j=2} S_{3h,j} \right) \cup \left(\bigcup_{j=1}^{j=4} S_{4h,j} \right) \cup \left(\bigcup_{j=1}^{j=8} S_{5h,j} \right) \cup \dots \cup \left(\bigcup_{j=1}^{j=2^{r-3}} S_{(r-1)h,j} \right) \cup \left(\bigcup_{j=1}^{j=2^{r-2}} S_{rh,j} \right) \cup \dots \quad (11)$$

$$\text{where } S_{mh,j} = \bigcup_{k=1}^{k=2} S_{m,jk}, \quad m \geq 3.$$

Let us assume that we continued such distribution of PPTs (and consequently of associated with them sets) from the fifth level till level $(r-1)$, and that this level supplies 2^{r-2} initial PPTs to level r . The number of distributed PPTs till level $(r-1)$ is supposed to be $[2, 4, \dots, 2^{r-3}, 2^{r-1}]$.

Uniqueness of distributed sets. Initial 2^{r-2} PPTs at level r produce $4 \times 2^{r-2} = 2^r$ PPTs. According to Lemma 6, the total set produced by 2^{r-2} PPTs, transferred from level $(r-1)$ to level r , is the same as the set produced by 2^r derived PPTs of level r . Effectively, as in the case of

considered above first five levels, we just substituted the former set by the latter. Thus, the set defined by distributed PPTs till level $(r - 1)$ is the same as the set produced by distributed PPTs till level r . According to our assumption, PPTs of level $(r - 1)$ define sets, which do not intersect with the sets defined by the rest of PPTs distributed till level $(r - 1)$. So, the sets defined by PPTs of level r also do not intersect with the latter sets. The sets produced by distributed PPTs of level r are unique at level r and have no duplicates (Lemma 6). Hence, all PPTs distributed till level r define unique sets with no duplicates.

The whole set W. PPTs distributed till level $(r - 1)$ define the whole set W . PPTs distributed till level r , and PPTs distributed till level $(r - 1)$, define the same sets. So, PPTs distributed till level r also define set W .

We can further divide PPTs of level r into two equal groups, each having accordingly 2^{r-1} PPTs. One group of PPTs remains at level r , while 2^{r-1} PPTs of the other group are used as initial PPTs for level $(r+1)$. This confirms our earlier assumed formula that the number of initial PPTs at an arbitrary level r , indeed, is equal to 2^{r-2} (for level $r + 1$ we should have according to this formula $2^{(r+1)-2} = 2^{r-1}$, and this is what we obtained).

The number of PPTs, distributed across sequential levels till level r , based on the above results, is accordingly (beginning from the second level) $2, 4, \dots, 2^{r-2}, 2^r$, which confirms the earlier assumed formula. If such a sequential distribution goes to infinity, then PPTs at level r are also divided into two equal groups, of which one remains at level r , and the other is used as initial PPTs for the next level $r+1$. So, in this case we also obtain the assumed sequence of the number of distributed PPTs (beginning from the second level): $[2, 4, \dots, 2^{r-2}, 2^{r-1}, \dots]$. It follows from the obtained formulas that in terms of united sets, produced by distributed PPTs, we indeed have formula (10) for the finite number of levels of distribution, and formula (11) when the number of levels of distribution is infinite.

Thus, for an arbitrary level r , we obtain the same attributes, which were assumed for level $(r - 1)$, which are as follows:

- (a) Formula 2^{r-2} for the number of initial PPTs;
- (b) Formulas for the number of distributed PPTs at each presentation level (both for finite and infinite number of presentation levels);
- (c) Formulas for the unions of sets, produced by distributed PPTs both for the finite and infinite number of levels;

- (d) Each of distributed PPTs produces a unique set among the sets produced by distributed PPTs, with no duplicates;
- (e) PPTs distributed beginning from the second level together produce a whole set W .

We also previously showed that the same attributes correspond to levels two to five. According to principle of mathematical induction, this means that the same attributes are associated with any arbitrary presentation level $r \geq 2$. Since level r is not limited by an upper boundary, such a distribution can go to infinity, so that all properties (a)-(e) remain in force in this case too.

It was explicitly shown that in case of finite number of presentation levels the distributed PPTs produce a whole set of pairs of odd integers W . The same is true when the number of distribution levels is infinite. However, the issue might look more subtle in this case. So, for this scenario the detailed proof of this important property of distributed PPTs will be provided later, in the property 5 of PPT's measure fraction.

Part 2. Distribution of several PPTs from an arbitrary level. First let us generalize the obtained results for the case of one original PPT residing at an arbitrary level $r \geq 2$, from which four PPTs are derived (above, in Part 1, these were four PPTs of level two). For the proof, we will apply very similar considerations as in Part 1 of this Lemma. The difference will be that in Part 1 we considered the whole set W , defined by all PPTs of the second level, while here we consider equality of the set defined by distributed PPTs to the set defined by the original PPTs.

One initial PPT, defining the original set S at an arbitrary level $r_0 + 1$ (where $r_0 \geq 0$, so that the first level is included too), produces four PPTs at level $(r_0 + 2)$, which are divided into two equal groups of two PPTs in each (similarly to the splitting of four PPTs of the second level in Part 1). Each of four PPTs defines unique at this level set with no duplicates (Lemma 5). Two PPTs of one group are used as initial PPTs for level $(r_0 + 3)$, accordingly producing eight PPTs, while two PPTs of the other group remain associated with level $(r_0 + 2)$. (The arrangement is similar to a situation earlier depicted in Fig. 3.) According to Lemma 6, the set defined by two initial PPTs is the same as the set defined by eight derived PPTs at level $(r_0 + 3)$. Now the original set, defined by one PPT of level $r_0 + 1$ (or by four PPTs of level $(r_0 + 2)$, since these sets are the same, according to Lemma 5), is defined by two PPTs of level $(r_0 + 2)$ and by eight PPTs of level $(r_0 + 3)$. Their union can be presented very similar to equation (14).

$$\bigcup_{i=1}^{i=4} s_{r_0+2,i} = \left(\bigcup_{i=1}^{i=2} s_{r_0+2,i} \right) \cup \left(\bigcup_{j=1}^{j=2} S_{r_0+3,j} \right), \text{ where } S_{r_0+3,j} = \bigcup_{k=1}^{k=4} s_{r_0+3,jk}$$

Uniqueness of distributed sets. According to Lemma 6, each of eight derived PPTs at level $(r_0 + 3)$ produces a unique set with no duplicates. However, the sets they produce effectively replaced the equivalent to them two sets, earlier produced by two unique PPTs at level $(r_0 + 2)$ (unique both at this level and among distributed PPTs). Consequently, eight derived PPTs produce a set unique among the sets produced by distributed PPTs. Since each of eight distributed PPTs of level $(r_0 + 3)$ produces a unique set with no duplicates (Lemma 6), all PPTs distributed from level two to level three produce unique sets with no duplicates.

The set S produced by distributed PPTs. According to Lemma 5, four PPTs of level $(r_0 + 2)$ produce the original set S . Distributed PPTs produce the same set as PPTs of level $(r_0 + 2)$, as it has been shown, that is the original set S .

Then, the first group of four PPTs of level $(r_0 + 3)$ is left at this level, while the second group of four PPTs is used as initial PPTs for level $(r_0 + 4)$, which accordingly defines sixteen PPTs of this level. We can apply the same considerations based on Lemma 6 about equality of sets defined by the initial and derived PPTs of level $(r_0 + 4)$. Then, we will find that the original set will be produced by two PPTs of level $(r_0 + 2)$, by four PPTs of level $(r_0 + 3)$, and by sixteen PPTs of level $(r_0 + 4)$, whose union can be presented similar to (16). Note that here we observe exactly the same pattern with regard to the number of initial PPTs and the number of distributed PPTs at each level, as when we started from the second presentation level in Part 1.

Distributed PPTs produce the same original set S. The proof is based on the fact that we replaced the set, produced by four PPTs of level $(r_0 + 3)$, by an equivalent set produced by sixteen PPTs of level $(r_0 + 4)$. (Equality of these sets follows from Lemma 6, since these sixteen PPTs were produced by four PPTs of level $(r_0 + 3)$.) Consequently, the set defined by distributed PPTs remains the same original set S . This can be presented as follows.

$$\bigcup_{i=1}^{i=4} s_{r_0+2,i} = \left(\bigcup_{i=1}^{i=2} s_{r_0+2,i} \right) \cup \left(\bigcup_{j=1}^{j=2} S_{(r_0+3)h,j} \right) \cup \left(\bigcup_{j=1}^{j=4} S_{r_0+4,j} \right), \text{ where } S_{(r_0+3)h,j} = \bigcup_{k=1}^{k=2} s_{(r_0+3),jk}, S_{r_0+4,j} = \bigcup_{k=1}^{k=4} s_{r_0+4,jk}$$

Uniqueness of distributed sets. Sixteen PPTs of level $(r_0 + 4)$ produce unique sets with no duplicates (Lemma 6). They replaced four unique sets with no duplicates earlier defined by four PPTs of level $(r_0 + 3)$ (these four sets at level $(r_0 + 3)$ are unique not only at level $(r_0 + 3)$, but also among all

PPTs distributed till level $(r_0 + 3)$, as it was shown). Consequently, sixteen PPTs of level $(r_0 + 4)$ also define sets (with no duplicates) unique among the sets defined by PPTs distributed till level $(r_0 + 4)$.

If we introduce parameter $r_1 = r - r_0$, where r is the current presentation level, $r \geq (r_0 + 2)$, then the number of initial PPTs for level r will be defined as 2^{r_1-2} , which mimics the formula 2^{r-2} when distribution started from the second level. The number of distributed PPTs at each subsequent level, which together define the original set produced by PPT at level $r_0 + 1$ (or by four PPTs at level $r_0 + 2$), is defined by similar sequence too. For the finite number of levels (beginning from level $r_0 + 2$, which corresponds to $r_1 = 2$), we have $[2, 4, \dots, 2^{r_1-2}, 2^{r_1}]$. When the number of levels goes to infinity, then the number of PPTs at subsequent levels is $[2, 4, \dots, 2^{r_1-2}, 2^{r_1-1}, \dots]$ (we have no upper boundary for r_1 in the same way, as we did not have an upper boundary for r in Part 1, so that such distribution can go to infinity).

The proof for a general case of an arbitrary level is based on method of mathematical induction. It is very similar to the proof considered in Part 1. We assume that the distribution of PPTs, which started at level $r_0 + 2$, continued till presentation level $(r_1 - 1)$, where $r_1 \geq 2$, and that the number of initial PPTs at this level is equal to 2^{r_1-3} , the number of PPTs at this level is 2^{r_1-1} , and distributed PPTs produce unique sets with no duplicates. We also assume that the set defined by PPTs distributed from level $(r_0 + 2)$ till level $(r_1 - 1)$ is the same as the set defined by the original PPT at level $r_0 + 1$.

According to our distribution algorithm, level $(r_1 - 1)$ supplies a half of its PPTs, that is $2^{r_1-1} / 2 = 2^{r_1-2}$, as initial PPTs to level r_1 . These initial PPTs accordingly produce $4 \times 2^{r_1-2} = 2^{r_1}$ PPTs of level r_1 . Consequently, if we stop distribution at this level, then the number of distributed PPTs, beginning from level $r_1 = 2$, is $[2, 4, \dots, 2^{r_1-2}, 2^{r_1}]$. If we continue distribution of PPTs to infinity, then the number of distributed PPTs accordingly becomes $[2, 4, \dots, 2^{r_1-2}, 2^{r_1-1}, \dots]$, since in this case derived PPTs of all levels are divided by half. So, we obtained the earlier assumed formulas for the number of initial PPTs at level r_1 , as well as formulas for the number of distributed PPTs both for the finite and infinite number of presentation levels.

According to Lemma 6, $4M$ PPTs of level r_1 , derived from M PPTs of level $(r_1 - 1)$, produce unique sets (let it be sets $s_{r_1,i}$) with no duplicates. The union of these sets produces the same set as the union of sets $s_{r_1-1,i}$ defined by initial PPTs.

$$\bigcup_{i=1}^M S_{r_1-1,i} = \bigcup_{j=1}^{4M} S_{r_1,j}$$

The set S produced by distributed PPTs. It follows from the above equality that the set, defined by PPTs distributed till level r_1 , is the same as the set defined by PPTs distributed till level $(r_1 - 1)$ (we just substituted the set defined by M PPTs of level $(r_1 - 1)$ by the set defined by $4M$ PPTs of level r_1 , which are the same). Thus, the addition of one more distribution level r_1 did not change the set defined by PPTs distributed till level $(r_1 - 1)$. The last set, according to our assumption, is the same as the set defined by the original PPT at level $r_0 + 1$. So, regardless of how many levels the original PPT is distributed across, the set defined by distributed PPTs remains the same set S .

Uniqueness of distributed sets. We assumed that each PPT distributed till level $(r_1 - 1)$ produces a unique set with no duplicates. Derived PPTs of level r_1 produce the same set as initial PPTs taken from level $(r_1 - 1)$. So, effectively, we replaced the unique set (among the sets produced by distributed PPTs) defined by M PPTs of level $(r_1 - 1)$, by the same unique set defined by $4M$ PPTs of level r_1 . $4M$ derived PPTs of level r_1 are unique at this level and have no duplicates (Lemma 6). So, since the sets defined by PPTs of level $(r_1 - 1)$ were unique and had no duplicates among the sets defined by distributed PPTs till level $(r_1 - 1)$, and they were replaced by equivalent unique sets of level r_1 , this means that the last sets are also unique among the sets distributed till level r_1 . Hence, all PPTs distributed till level r_1 produce unique sets with no duplicates.

Previously, we showed that the same properties are true for levels $(r_0 + 2)$, $(r_0 + 3)$, $(r_0 + 4)$ which corresponds to $r_1 = \{2,3,4\}$. According to principle of mathematical induction, the assumed properties and formulas are true for an arbitrary level $r_1 \geq 2$. This mathematically legitimizes distribution of one PPT beginning from an arbitrary level.

It follows from the above that we can take several (let it be K) PPTs of one original level r_0 (not necessarily a complete set of PPTs) and distribute each of them across subsequent levels, either till a final level, or to infinity. Each distributed PPT obtained this way will define a unique set with no duplicates (unique among *all* distributed PPTs corresponding to all K PPTs of original level r_0). Indeed, each PPT at the same original level r_0 , according to Lemma 6, defines a unique set with no duplicates at this level. Each such PPT produces a branch of distributed PPTs. Within the branch, distributed PPTs together define the same set as their initial PPT, while each distributed PPT defines a unique set (both assertions were proved above). Since the sets produced by PPTs of original level

r_0 are unique, each of the distributed PPTs produces a set unique not only within its branch, but also among the sets produced by distributed PPTs of all branches. Let define a set corresponding to one i -th initial PPT at level r_0 as $s_{r_0,i}$, and the union of sets, corresponding to distributed PPTs of this i -th initial PPT as $S_{d,i}$. Using the earlier obtained result about equality of sets produced by the initial PPT and by its distributed PPTs, we can write $s_{r_0,i} = S_{d,i}$. Since the sets $s_{r_0,i}$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, K$, are unique, they do not intersect. All distributed sets are unique too, and consequently do not intersect as well, which in turn means that the sets $S_{d,i}$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, K$, defined by distributed PPTs within each distribution branch, do not intersect. For the union of non-intersecting sets, the following equality is fulfilled.

$$\bigcup_{i=1}^K s_{r_0,i} = \bigcup_{i=1}^K S_{d,i}$$

Thus, together distributed PPTs define the same set of pairs of odd integers as all PPTs of the original level r_0 . This proves that, indeed, we can distribute several PPTs of one level without changing the set defined by the chosen PPTs of the original level.

This completes the proof of Lemma.

Note: The distribution of PPTs of the initial level can be done in different ways. For instance, instead of dividing PPTs into equal groups, we can use unequal groups, leaving PPTs of one group at the same level, and transforming PPTs of another group to the next level. On that next level, we again can divide PPTs into unequal groups, and so on. The important thing is that regardless of how we create groups of PPTs, PPTs distributed across different levels together produce the same set, as PPTs of the original level do.

Note: (Division of the number of PPTs by two.) In Lemma 7, we always split the number of PPTs of the last level of distribution by half. It is possible for any presentation level, since the number of derived PPTs at the next level increases by *four-fold* (see Note 3), while we need division *by two*, and so the last operation is always possible. Such, at the second level we have four derived PPTs, at the third level eight PPTs, and so on.

Eventually, we want to prove that the sets (10), (11), corresponding to distributed complete set of PPTs, represent a *whole set* of pairs of odd integers W . Not an easy task if we intend to operate on infinite sets of pairs of odd integers. However, in our case the aforementioned sets are *derivatives* of PPTs. Lemmas 3-7 established unambiguous relationships of PPTs with their corresponding sets,

which allows us to operate on PPTs instead of considering only sets of pairs of odd integers. However, we still need some additional ties of PPTs with the sets they define.

So far, we considered only the number of PPTs constituting a complete set either of PPTs, or part of PPTs of certain presentation levels. Below, we introduce another characteristic of PPTs, the PPTs' *measure*.

2.4. PPT's measure (fraction) and its properties

Lemmas 5 - 7 give us the basis for introducing PPT's *measure* and defining its properties. Two properties are of especial importance to us. First, according to Lemma 6, complete sets of PPTs of the same level together produce the *whole* set of pairs of odd integers W . In this regard, all presentation levels are *equivalent*. Second, any PPT of a lower presentation level can be presented as a combination of PPTs distributed at higher levels (Lemma 7).

Definition of a PPT measure fraction. The number of all PPTs P_r at an arbitrary level r is $P_r = 4^{r-1}$ (see Note 3). Then, the measure f , called *fraction*, is defined for one PPT as $f = 1 / P_r = 1 / 4^{r-1}$. For K PPTs from the same level, the fraction is accordingly $f(K) = K / P_r = K / 4^{r-1}$.

Note that according to the given definition, a fraction is a positive number, unless the set of chosen PPTs (the number in numerator) is empty, in which case $f(0) = 0$.

Let us remind that we consider only fractions corresponding to *non-intersecting* PPTs. As it was found in Lemmas 5-7, for upward transformation of PPTs this condition is fulfilled. At the same level, PPTs do not intersect too (meaning non-intersection of produced by them sets), according to Lemma 6. We need operations on PPTs residing at different presentation levels, foremost additivity property, and conditions when combinations of PPTs correspond to the whole set of pairs of odd integers W . Here, we consider levels $r \geq 1$, that is r can be an arbitrary big number and go to infinity. As a measure, fraction has the following properties.

1. For a complete set of PPTs of one level, the total fraction is equal to one.

Proof: The total number of PPTs of one level, defining non-intersecting sets, is equal to 4^{r-1} at any level $r \geq 1$. Thus, for any r from the range of definition we have $f(4^{r-1}) = 4^{r-1} / P_r = 4^{r-1} / 4^{r-1} = 1$.

It also follows from this result that the maximum possible value of a fraction is *one*.

2. *Fraction has a property of additivity.*

Proof: Let K and M be the number of PPTs at level r . Then, for any $r \geq 1$ we have

$$f(K) = K / 4^{r-1}, f(M) = M / 4^{r-1}$$

We can write

$$f(K) + f(M) = K / 4^{r-1} + M / 4^{r-1} = (K + M) / 4^{r-1} = f(K + M)$$

This proves the additivity property of fraction.

3. *The fraction does not change its value if the corresponding to this fraction PPTs are transformed to another presentation level.*

Proof: Let us consider levels $r_1 \geq 1$ and $r_2 \geq 2$ (note that both levels do not have an upper boundary); $r_2 > r_1$. The fraction of K_{r_1} PPTs at level r_1 is $f_{r_1}(K_{r_1}) = K_{r_1} / 4^{r_1-1}$. When transformed to a higher level $r_2 > r_1$ (which we can do according to Lemma 6), the number of PPTs becomes $K_{r_2} = K_{r_1} \times 4^{r_2-r_1}$ (the number of PPTs is multiplied by four at each next level, see Note 3).

Accordingly, the fraction f_{r_2} at level r_2 is as follows

$$f_{r_2}(K_{r_2}) = f_{r_2}(K_{r_1} \times 4^{r_2-r_1}) = K_{r_1} \times 4^{r_2-r_1} / 4^{r_2-1} = K_{r_1} / 4^{r_1-1} = f_{r_1}(K_{r_1}),$$

This proves property 3.

4. *The sum of fractions corresponding to non-intersecting PPTs does not depend on how these PPTs are distributed across presentation levels.*

Proof: We assume that *initial* PPTs of all considered distributed PPTs reside at *finite* levels, even if PPTs' distribution then goes to infinity. For such initial PPTs we can use the following approach.

Let $\{f_{r_1}, f_{r_2}, \dots, f_{r_s}\}$ be fractions of non-intersecting initial PPTs at presentation levels $\{r_1 < r_2 < \dots < r_s\}$. According to Lemma 6, all these PPTs can be transformed to the highest level r_s . Since, according to property 3, fractions of these PPTs do not change during such transformations, we can write $f_{r_1} = f_{r_s}^{r_1}$, $f_{r_2} = f_{r_s}^{r_2}$, \dots , $f_{r_s} = f_{r_s}^{r_s}$, where fractions $\{f_{r_s}^{r_i}\}$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, s$, correspond to PPTs transformed from levels $\{r_i\}$ to level r_s . According to additivity property 2, then we can add the fractions of PPTs transformed to level r_s , so that

$$\sum_{i=1}^s f_{r_i} = \sum_{i=1}^s f_{r_s}^{r_i}$$

Let us denote $F_s = \sum_{i=1}^s f_{r_s}^{r_i}$. Using definition of a fraction, we can find the total number of PPTs K at level r_s , corresponding to F_s , as $K = F_s \times P_r = 4^{r-1} F_s$. According to Lemma 6, the sets defined by these PPTs are unique (non-intersecting) and have no duplicates. Given definition of the fraction, to each PPT at level r_s corresponds fraction $f_s = 1/4^{r-1}$. If such a fraction is distributed to a final level $r_s + R$, then we can find the total fraction (the sum of fractions of thus distributed PPT) as follows. In the distribution algorithm of PPTs, considered in Lemma 7, we leave half of PPTs (1/2) at the current level, and transfer the other half of PPTs (also 1/2) to the next level. The fraction is the ratio of the number of chosen PPTs at the current level to the total number of PPTs at this level. Then such a splitting of PPTs means that the fraction of the current level is equally divided between the current and the next levels. At the next level we again divide the number of PPTs by two and repeat the procedure, leaving one half at this level, and transferring the other half of PPTs to the next level. Thus, at each level the fraction is divided by two, except for the last level $r_s + R$, whose PPTs are not divided but are all left at this last level. So, the corresponding to this level fraction will be the same as the fraction of PPTs left at the previous level. Let $\varphi_{s,s+R}$ be the total fraction of such distributed PPTs, where the first index denotes the starting level, and the second index denotes the final distribution level. Then we can write the following.

$$\varphi_{s,s+R} = f_s (1/2 + 1/4 + \dots + 1/2^{R+1}) + f_s (1/2^{R+1})$$

The sum in the round brackets represents a sum of geometrical progression with a common ratio of 1/2, the first term of 1/2, and the number of summands $R + 1$. Calculating this sum, we find

$$\varphi_{s,s+R} = f_s (1 - 1/2^{R+1}) + f_s (1/2^{R+1}) = f_s$$

So, when one initial PPT of level r_s is distributed to a final level $r_s + R$, the total fraction of distributed PPTs remains the same. According to Lemma 7, the sets of pairs of odd integers, produced by several PPTs distributed from one level, do not intersect. Thus, each fraction f_s corresponds to PPTs defining unique set with no duplicates.

Now consider distribution of one PPT of level r_s to infinity. In this case, the fraction of each level is divided by two, so that we can write

$$\varphi_{s,\infty} = f_s (1/2 + 1/4 + \dots + 1/2^{R+1} + \dots) = f_s \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} (1/2)^i = f_s (1/2) / (1 - 1/2) = f_s$$

Here, we calculated the sum of an infinitely decreasing geometric progression with a common ratio of $1/2$ and the first term of $1/2$. So, we obtained that $\varphi_{s,\infty} = \varphi_{s,s+R} = f_s$. Thus, the fraction of distributed to infinity PPTs, corresponding to one initial PPT of level r_s , is also equal to f_s - same as for the distribution to a final level.

So, we proved that the total fraction of distributed PPTs, corresponding to one initial PPT of level r_s , is equal to a fraction of this initial PPT. We know that the sets corresponding to distributed PPTs do not intersect (Lemma 7). So, in order to find the total fraction of all distributed PPTs, we can sum up fractions φ_s corresponding to K distribution branches of PPTs earlier transformed to level r_s .

Let denote $\varphi_s = \varphi_{s,\infty} = \varphi_{s,s+R}$. Summing up K fractions φ_s , and substituting the earlier found values of f_s and K , we find their total fraction Φ_s .

$$\Phi_s = \varphi_s \times K = f_s \times K = (1/4^{r-1}) \times 4^{r-1} F_s = F_s$$

So, the total fraction Φ_s of distributed PPTs is the same as the total fraction F_s of PPTs, transformed to level r_s from previous levels, that is $\Phi_s = F_s$. However, the total fraction F_s is the same as the total fraction of all original PPTs, distributed at the beginning across different levels. So, we obtain that the sum of fractions of non-intersecting PPTs, indeed, does not depend on how these PPTs are distributed across presentation levels. This proves property 4.

Note: It follows from the property of measure 4 that if one distributes PPT of the first level (whose fraction f_1 is equal to one) across subsequent levels to infinity, then the sum of fractions of such distributed to infinity PPTs will be equal to one as well. Indeed, in this case we have

$$\varphi_{2,\infty} = f_1(1/2 + 1/4 + \dots + 1/2^{R+1} + \dots) = 1 \times \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} (1/2)^i = 1 \tag{12}$$

The next property is an important one. Suppose one obtained an infinite number of "no solution" fractions for some equation, and wants to prove that all these "no solution" fractions summarily exhausts all hypothetically possible integer solutions of this equation, which would mean that this equation has no integer solutions at all.

5. The total fraction value of one, when obtained by summation of fractions of non-intersecting PPTs, corresponds to a whole set of pairs of odd integers.

Proof: Let us consider finite levels first. We assume that this property is not valid, and we have a set S of pairs of odd integers produced by distributed PPTs, whose total fraction is equal to one, but this set S does not correspond to the whole set W . According to property 4, the total fraction of these PPTs is equal to the total sum of fractions of those PPTs transformed to one highest level (let it be level s), that is also to one. If the combination of transformed PPTs at level s does not define the whole set of pairs of odd integers, this could only mean that some pairs or subsets of pairs of odd integers are excluded, which in turn means that some PPTs are excluded from the complete set of PPTs at this level. The latter is because according to Corollary 1 any pair of odd integers at any presentation level is defined by some PPT. Indeed, if some PPTs were not excluded, then the set of PPTs would be complete. However, all complete sets of PPTs, according to Lemma 6, define the *whole* set of pairs of odd integers W . Thus, the incomplete set of pairs of odd integers can be defined by only incomplete set of PPTs, so that their number M has to be less than the number of PPTs $P = 4^{s-1}$ in a complete set of PPTs, that is $M < P$. Then, the fraction of PPTs at level s , which define the set S , is equal to $M/P = M/4^{s-1} < 1$, since $M < P$. However, according to our assumption, the fraction of PPTs producing the set S is equal to one. The obtained contradiction means that our initial assumption is invalid, and the set S , defined by non-intersecting PPTs whose fraction is equal to one, in fact presents a whole set of pairs of odd integers W .

Now we will consider an infinite number of summed up fractions f_i , $i = 1, 2, \dots$, when presentation levels go to infinity. We assume that these fractions initially corresponded to M non-intersecting PPTs of one level, some or all of which then were distributed across different levels to infinity (we can do this according to Lemma 7). (If the initial PPTs were not at the same level, they can be transformed to one level according to property 4.) Let the sum of these fractions $\sum_{i=1}^{\infty} f_i = 1$. PPTs, corresponding to these fractions, define set S of pairs of odd integers. Note that equality of the infinite sum to one also means that the sum of fractions f_{0h} , $h = 1, 2, \dots, M$, of the original M PPTs is also equal to one, according to properties 3 and 4, that is $\sum_{h=1}^M f_{0h} = 1$. We assume that the set S is incomplete, that is it *does not* define the whole set of pairs of odd integers W , and some pair (or pairs) of odd integers is excluded.

The excluded pair of odd integers, according to Corollary 1, corresponds to some PPT with fraction f_{k_0} at some level k_0 (at or above the initial level). According to definition of fraction, $f_{k_0} > 0$. Let us call this PPT as PPT_{ex} . This fraction f_{k_0} is excluded from our infinite sum of fractions - otherwise PPT_{ex} would belong to the set of PPTs corresponding to infinite sum of

fractions, and consequently the excluded pair would belong to the set S , which contradicts the assumption that this pair is excluded from the set S .

The distributed PPTs originated from one level. So, according to Lemma 6, we can transform these initial M PPTs into K PPTs at level k_0 , where PPT_{ex} with fraction f_{k_0} resides. According to properties 3 and 4, for these K PPTs at level k_0 we have $\sum_{j=1}^K f_{tj} = \sum_{h=1}^M f_{0h} = \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} f_i = 1$, where f_{tj} are fractions of K transformed PPTs at level k_0 . It was proved in Lemma 6 that there can be no duplicate pairs at the same level of presentation, so that *none of the pairs* defined by PPT_{ex} with a fraction f_{k_0} has a duplicate at level k_0 . Thus, at level k_0 , the set of pairs of odd integers, defined by PPT_{ex} , does not intersect with the sets, defined by K PPTs at level k_0 . So, we have a set of non-intersecting PPTs at level k_0 , whose fractions we can sum up. If we add at this level the sum of fractions $\sum_{j=1}^K f_j = 1$, and a fraction f_{k_0} , we obtain $f_{k_0} + \sum_{j=1}^K f_j > 1$. However, these summed up fractions correspond to non-intersecting PPTs, as it was shown above, and at the same time belong to the same level. According to property 1 of measure, and to the Note in discussion of property 4, such a sum of fractions cannot be greater than one. The obtained contradiction means that our assumption is invalid, and in case of infinite number of fractions, whose sum is equal to one and which correspond to non-intersecting PPTs, these PPTs define a whole set of pairs of odd integers W . This proves property 5.

The found properties of PPT fractions, together with the definition of PPTs and Lemmas describing its properties, define the notion of PPT.

3. Why the infinite sum of one of fractions of distributed PPTs defines the whole set of pairs of odd integers

The deterministic nature of the summed fractions. We would like to emphasize one more time that we deal with *deterministic* values, which are the fractions corresponding to each presentation level, so that their sum is a *deterministic* value too. It was discussed earlier that the invalid assumption of some people about the stochastic nature of the sum could come from the notion of asymptotic densities [1,2]. However, in our case, we consider *PPTs* whose fraction is a *deterministic* value. Each PPT defines an infinite set of pairs of odd integers, this is true, but the sum, like (12), relates to not these infinite sets, *but to PPTs' fractions*, and *only* to these fractions. The notion of asymptotic densities *was not* applied to fractions (and actually it cannot be applied), and so *it is not* used here.

3.1. Notes about sums of infinite series and their properties

In this section, we present additional explanations why the value of one of the infinite sum of distributed fractions in (12) corresponds to the *whole* set of pairs of odd integers W without duplicates, even though the answer was already given by property 5 of fraction. The reason for raising this question is a peculiar treatment of the notion of sums of infinite series by some people, which we will call "Zeno's approach" below. Such a view assumes that the obtained value of one means that the sum of distributed fractions in (12) only *tends* to one, but not that it *is* the sum of fractions. Accepting such a view would mean that the sum will never reach the value of one; there will always exist a PPT, however small its fraction is, which still could contain a pair of odd integers outside the subsets defined by distributed across subsequent levels PPTs. What is not realized in such an assumption is that in our case of infinitely decreasing geometrical progression its sum can be less than one *only* for a finite number of fractions, or if some infinitesimally small terms of geometrical progression (summed up in (12)) are removed. However, this is not our case - we have a full infinite set of geometrical progression's terms, represented by formula (12), which are *all* summed up, to infinity, so that there could be no more terms to sum up beyond infinity, and consequently no more PPTs with pairs of odd integers, which hypothetically could be outside of subsets defined by distributed PPTs, could exist.

Understanding the notion of sums of infinite series. This is an issue, which is linked to a rather methodological level, how one understands the sums of infinite series. Geometric progression presents a particular case of sums of infinite series, which are used in many applications. Sums of infinite series are invaluable toolsets, and in some instances foundations of whole subjects in many disciplines. In these sums, the obtained value is *equal* to the sum of infinite series.

Consider the *discrete geometric distribution*, defined as a sum of infinite series, whose value is *equal* to one. A lack of equality to one would violate one of the main axioms of Probability theory, that the probability over the full set $x = 0, 1, \dots$ must be *equal* to one. The same is true for *Poisson distribution*, which is also a sum of infinite series. (This argument alone should be sufficient to convince any reasonably thinking doubter that the sum of an infinite geometrical progression is *equal* to the obtained value, but not that it only *tends* to it.)

Though it may not be as popular in number theory, the *equality*, not tendency, of sums of infinite series is a core concept in calculus, such as Taylor Expansion or Maclaurin Series, which are also the sums of infinite series with non-zero elements, and where *equality* between the functions

these series represent and the sums of infinite series are of fundamental importance. Fourier series is another example where the sums of infinite series are *equal* to represented functions.

3.2. The mathematical underpinnings of Zeno's paradox

In fact, the aforementioned Zeno's followers see the sum of infinite series in the frame of a famous Zeno's paradox, when Achilles is trying to catch up a tortoise, but allegedly will never do. Suppose the tortoise stands in front of Achilles at a distance d_0 , and both begin moving simultaneously in the same direction; Achilles with a speed of a , and the tortoise with a lesser speed of c . When Achilles comes to a point where the tortoise started, it will move some distance away. When Achilles reaches that point, the tortoise moves still farther apart, and so on. Thus, concludes Zeno, Achilles will never catch up the tortoise, because there will be always some distance between them.

It follows from the laws of kinematic motion that Achilles will catch up the tortoise in time interval $t_k = d_0 / (a - c)$, travelling the distance

$$d_k = at_k = ad_0 / (a - c) \quad (13)$$

For mathematical formulation of Zeno's paradox, we should sum up time intervals $\{t_i\}$, $i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, \infty$, required for Achilles to travel first the distance d_0 , and then all subsequent decreasing stretches $\{d_i\}$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, \infty$, the tortoise makes while Achilles travels the previous stretch.

$$t_{cZeno} = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} t_i = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} (d_i / a) = d_0 / a + [c(d_0 / a)] / a + [c(d_0 c / a^2)] / a + [c(d_0 c^2 / a^3)] / a + \dots = (d_0 / a) [1 + (c / a) + (c / a)^2 + (c / a)^3 + \dots] = (d_0 / a) \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} (c / a)^i = (d_0 / a) \left[\frac{1}{(1 - c / a)} \right] = (d_0 / a) \left[\frac{a}{(a - c)} \right] = d_0 / (a - c)$$

In the above sum, we use a formula for a sum of infinite geometrical progression with a common ratio c / a and the first term of one. The calculation gives the time interval $t_{cZeno} = d_0 / (a - c)$, when Achilles catches up the tortoise, which is exactly the same result as the independent kinematic approach produced in (13). Thus, we obtained that $t_{cZeno} = t_k$. Therefore, the nature of Zeno's paradox is in using different mathematical methods for calculating the same value. However, at Zeno's time the mathematical notion of sums of infinite series was yet to be developed. If he knew the modern mathematical notion of sums of infinite series, there would be no Zeno's paradox.

So, what we did above is calculating the infinite sum of decreasing time intervals t_i , that is

$$t_{cZeno} = \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} t_i = t(\infty) = d_0 / (a - c) \quad (14)$$

What is important for us in (14), is the *mathematical legitimacy* of the **equality** in expression $t_{cZeno} = t(\infty) = d_0 / (a - c)$. In other words, that the value of $d_0 / (a - c)$ **is** the sum of an infinite number of decreasing time intervals, but not that this sum only **tends** to $d_0 / (a - c)$, but never reaches it. Kinematic formulas, as we have seen, confirm this *equality*.

Both the kinematic approach and the sum of infinite series we used are equally legitimate and valid approaches from the perspective of modern calculus. One even should not bother with the kinematic approach once the sum of infinite series is calculated. In our case, we mentioned it just for people having problem with understanding that the sums of infinite series are *equal* to values and functions they represent, but not only *tend* to them. (We would not pay so much attention to the issue, unless there were people, which think about such limits indeed as of *tendencies*, but not *equalities*.)

Certainly, in the same way the sum of an infinitely decreasing geometrical progression produces equality *in a general case*, but not the *tendency* to some value. (For convenience, let's assume that all elements of the geometrical progression are positive, which is our case.) When the number of summed up terms is finite, or one or more infinitesimal elements in a sum of infinite number of summands are missed, this is *tendency*. When the number of summed up elements in a geometrical progression is infinite and all elements are present, this is *equality*. If we do not agree that this is a valid equality, then we should agree that Achilles, indeed, will never catch up the tortoise. There are no other alternatives. But such an assumption is obviously untrue. Achilles catches up the tortoise, as everybody knows and as it was shown above. Both mathematical approaches we considered produced the same result. One should not have problems with a kinematic approach - it is simple and obvious. Then the second approach is right if and only if the sum of infinite numbers of terms of a geometrical progression is considered as *equality*, but not as the tendency - and this is what the modern calculus assumes.

Similarly, one can ask, what is the area between the curve e^{-x} and the axis x on the interval $[0, \infty)$? The answer is given by the integral $\int_0^{\infty} e^{-x} dx = -(e^{-\infty} - 1) = 1$. It's unlikely that someone would say that this is the tendency to equality, but not the equality itself, since the case is more obvious. However, this integral with infinite upper boundary and the sum of decreasing infinite geometrical progression are mathematical vehicles based on the *same idea* of *equality* of the found sums (an integral is a sum of infinite number of infinitesimals) to the actual values in question.

It seems that part of the considered problem relates to methodological approach in teaching calculus, when the definition of a limit that uses ε -intervals is uncritically transferred to sums of

infinite series, without emphasizing that the calculated value of such a sum represents the *actual value* of the sum, but not the *limit* defined in ε -terms, the sum only tends to.

5. Conclusion

We provided a formalization of the introduced concept of a producing term (producing infinite or finite sets of integer numbers), applied mostly to *pairs of producing terms* (PPT) for infinite sets of pairs of odd integers. Similarly, one can consider other combinations of producing terms with two or more producing terms.

The application of the introduced concept and its formalized apparatus, in the author's opinion, can be quite wide. There are equations, which in principle allow dividing the set of possible solutions into several finite or infinite subsets using specific initial or boundary conditions, which may facilitate finding a solution or proving its absence. Then, such subsets can be united using the proposed approaches. As the presented examples show, such unification can be not simple, especially in case of combining infinite number of infinite sets. In such situations, the introduced formalization can be very helpful both in terms of choosing the method how to approach the problem, as well as using the developed and presented in this paper technical apparatus.

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